

SPIDER

EU-LAC Digital Partnership

D.1.2 - Mapping of digital dialogues and identified EU-LAC agreements. Interim version

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full Name
AECID	Spanish Agency for International Development
AgTechs	Agricultural Technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALCE	Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency
APEC	Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation
BELLA	Building the Europe Link to Latin America
BMZ	German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development
CELAC	Community of Latin American and Caribbean States
DEI	Diversity, Equality and Inclusion
D4D	Digital for Development
EC	European Commission
ECSG	Electronic Commerce Steering Group
EdTechs	Educational Technology
EU	European Union
FinTechs	Financial (Services) Technology
GÉANT	Pan-European research and education network that interconnects Europe's National Research and Education Networks
HLPF	High-Level Political Forum
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IICA	Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture
IDB	Inter-American Development Bank
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IXPs	Internet Exchange Points
JIRI	EU-CELAC Joint Initiative on Research and Innovation
KICs	Knowledge and Innovation Communities

LAC	Latin America and the Caribbean
MERCOSUR	Southern Common Market (Mercado Común del Sur)
NREN	National Research and Education Networks
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OTT	Over-the-top ¹
R&I	Research and Innovation
RedCLARA	Latin American Cooperation of Advanced Networks (Redes de educación - Cooperación Latino Americana de Redes Avanzadas)
ResInfra	EU-LAC Partnership in Research Infrastructures
RFOs	Research Funding Organisations
RPOs	Research performing Organisation
STI	Science, Technology and Innovation
TICAL	Technology Information Conference For Administrative Leadership
VRE	Virtual Research Environments

¹ Here: OTT rules regulate digital media and prescribe a code of ethics along with classification standards to be followed by the publishers of news, current affairs and online curated content.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This interim version of the mapping of digital dialogues and EU-LAC agreements tries to capture and showcase the work already undertaken by the SPIDER consortium in order to provide a screenshot of the digital transformation landscape between the European Union and Latin America and the Caribbean. There are many different dialogues and commitments ongoing on various different levels, such as on the EU-LAC regional level, but also between the EU and single LAC countries or specific LAC countries and EU members states, e.g. Brazil and Germany (just as one example) or the multilateral level such as MERCOSUR, the Pacific Alliance or the United Nations even. This interim version of the deliverable of Spider tries to capture way of how these vast dialogues and resulting commitments can best be analysed and what is the most efficient way to approach this and the most important take-aways. The focus is set on (1) main actors involved in the dialogues, (2) different themes and key areas mentioned around digital dialogues, such as AI, 5G, blockchain, virtual research environments etc., (3) practical applications such as accelerators, hubs or software platforms deriving from the dialogues as well as (4) resulting commitments such as such as next steps and following dialogues, upcoming funding programmes or working groups.

The report tries not to analyse already all of the identified dialogues or commitments, but rather to spark a development for the following months leading to a final version of this report in June 2025 and what could be the best way of approaching this task. Thus, it represents a draft version or status quo of the ongoing work and is to be seen as a living document further to assess the work. It is welcomed by the SPIDER consortium and the authors of this report to receive notifications on ongoing digital dialogues and resulting commitments in order to provide a supportive more comprehensive analysis in June 2025.

1. INTRODUCTION

The mapping provides an outline of the digital transformation landscape. It analyses relevant commitments resulting from bilateral, regional and multilateral dialogues between Europe and LAC. Furthermore, it comprises common bi-regional thematic priorities related to digital transformation technologies. The ones addressed by SPIDER are AI, 5G, Blockchain, Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity and Virtual Research Environments (VRE).

Through a screening process, SPIDER will focus on the analysis of key commitments resulting from digital dialogues between Europe and Brazil, Mexico and Argentina (i.e. Argentina Digital Agenda 2030). Moreover, we will also consider the commitments from the Pacific Alliance, MERCOSUR Digital, EU-LAC Digital Economy Dialogue, EU-LAC Digital Alliance, Digital Agenda for LAC (2024), EU-CELAC Strategic Roadmap on STI (2021-2023) and BELLA's Open Dialogues Sessions (ODS), among others. The screening process of dialogues (including declarations, position papers, action plans and roadmaps) comprises interlinked data collection related to digital transformation and analysis that will be performed both in EU and LAC country contexts. In total, between 8 and 10 dialogues, and between 50-120 bilateral, regional and multilateral agreements (or action plans, guidelines, statements etc.) will be analysed.

The whole mapping and review will cover two deliverables in two different time frames

1. Initial draft mapping in Month 6, April 2024.
2. Final version in Month 20, June 2025.

Key information from this Task is the identification of the main actors involved on digital dialogues and agreements, main themes, practical applications and commitments deriving from them.

Different steps to achieve the screening results have been undertaken:

- Collecting initial information on digital dialogues from partners through an excel sheet.
- Two co-creation workshops with the project partners.
- Initial screening of additional dialogues included in the concept note D1.1.
- Interim version of the mapping (D1.2).
- Follow up of identified dialogues and agreements and review by all partners until the final version of the mapping (D1.3, due in month 20).

1.1. *About the SPIDER Project*

SPIDER aims to support the exploitation of the full potential of the newly established BELLA network and the implementation of the outcomes of EU-LAC dialogues in the context of digitalisation and R&I.

SPIDER proposes a multi-stakeholder approach to enable the development of an EU-LAC strategic partnership. SPIDER will engage relevant R&I stakeholders from EU and LAC more actively and strategically in supporting dialogues and creating a common and orchestrated vision and strategy for the exploitation of the full potential of BELLA network and the implementation of the outcomes of digital dialogues enhancing EU-LAC cooperation in R&I.

SPIDER adopts a human-centred and participatory approach, combined with an inclusive and intersectional perspective to support the development of strategic partnerships to stimulate the use of digital technologies that can benefit from BELLA and are relevant for EU-LAC R&I cooperation.

At the core of this strategy is the EU-LAC Digital Dialogues Implementation Forum (DIF) that is unique of its kind in international cooperation in R&I and will serve as a multi-stakeholder platform to foster dialogues and exchange of best practices to support the

implementation of digital dialogues’ commitments. Furthermore, DIF Working Groups will support the adoption of a human-centred approach to technology development, alongside Diversity, Equality and Inclusion (DEI) principles. Coupled with this, SPIDER will assess the use of BELLA and identify pathways for its future exploitation by engaging key actors of the digital ecosystem in project activities. Moreover, SPIDER will implement a Twinning Programme to foster digital partnerships by connecting EU and LAC innovation hubs that can seize the opportunities of BELLA for digital transformation. On top of that, a cascade of events, including Dialogue Forum events, focus groups, call for ideas, webinars and workshops, demo-days and a final conference will support the project actions.

2. Sources

The content for this review and mapping and subsequent updates will be based on different sources:

As a first step and team-effort by the consortium, an excel feedback on the participation and identification of dialogues for EU-LAC digital transformation, identification of current bi-regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I, the most important actors as well as the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation was sent around to be filled out by partners. This Excel Sheet has been sent around by INMARK in November 2023 to all partners for their feedback collection.

Name	E-mail	Institution	Have you participated in Dialogues for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. If yes, indicate the name and year of dialogue	Please indicate current bi regional and/or national policies, strategies and funding programmes related to R&I	Name the most important actors to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Name the main barriers to EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation	Observations/Comments
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Figure 1 - Excel sheet sent around to partners for collective feedback

Following was a Co-creation Workshop on 14th December 2023 organized by CEDIA for all partners to contribute for the concept note and also different parts for the mapping of dialogues.

After this, a second workshop on developing the indicators for monitoring the dialogue outcomes was held during the SPIDER consortium meeting in Madrid on February 23rd, 2024 in Madrid, Spain. This workshop was attended by all consortium partners.

For the purpose of the concept note (D1.1) an initial set of dialogues and commitments was analysed, mostly by CEDIA.

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
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Figure 2 - Table for initial set of dialogues and commitments

This deliverable D1.2 tries to capture the steps and work so far undergone in the upcoming following sections. It also analyses an initial exemplary set of dialogues and commitments in a deeper way.

For the upcoming months after the interim version and for the final review and mapping of the dialogues and commitments it is foreseen to provide a very comprehensive list to be shared for the European Commission and partner countries to be used. It will entail the following parts:

Website link

- Characteristics
- Countries/institutions involved (EU/CELAC)
- Type of agreement

- Signature date/still in force
- Digital transformation or related approach addressed
- Original Text/ English
- link to document
- Main Actors (stakeholders) mentioned
- Themes mentioned
- Practical Applications
- Resulting Commitments
- Budget (for resulting commitments or practical applications, if mentioned)

Website link	Characteristics	Countries/institutions involved (EU/CELAC)	Type of agreement	Signature date/still in force	Digital transformation or related approach
Original Text/ English link to document	Main Actors (stakeholders) mentioned	Themes mentioned	Practical Applications	Resulting Commitments	Budget (if mentioned)

Figure 3 - Excel headlines for collecting the dialogues' and commitments' features

3. Methodology

The concept note for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation (D1.1) describes the initial process for the screening and mapping of the digital dialogues and resulting commitments. For illustrative purposes this is reviewed here in the following two sections.

3.1.1. Development of indicators to monitor dialogue outcomes

In order to establish qualitative indicators for the assessment and monitoring of dialogue outcomes implementation across the BELLA countries in Latin America, a workshop was conducted on February 23rd, 2024 in Madrid. This workshop adopted a collaborative approach, integrating ideas generated during a brainstorming session centered around six key questions, resulting in the creation of three qualitative indicators for each question, aided by artificial intelligence within the context of the ideas proposed in the workshop.

The trigger questions were strategically positioned within a Miro Board to stimulate the ideation process among participants, as depicted in the accompanying illustration:

Figure 4 Miro Board - Defining qualitative indicators to assess and monitor the status of dialogues outcomes implementation across the BELLA countries in LAC

The qualitative indicators derived from the collaborative co-creation process offers valuable insights into assessing and monitoring the implementation of dialogue outcomes across the BELLA countries in Latin America. One of the fundamental reflections drawn from these indicators is the critical role of stakeholder satisfaction and engagement. By measuring stakeholders' satisfaction levels and their active involvement in the dialogue process, essential feedback is gathered to evaluate the effectiveness and inclusivity of the dialogue initiatives. This underscores the importance of fostering collaborative relationships and ensuring that diverse voices are heard throughout the implementation process.

Besides, the emphasis on assessing policy influence and long-term impact highlights the need for dialogue outcomes to drive meaningful changes and sustainable improvements in targeted areas. It is important to not only track immediate policy changes but also evaluate the lasting effects of dialogue initiatives, ensuring their relevance and effectiveness over time. Furthermore, the incorporation of expert opinions and the exploration of existing best practices and frameworks underscore the importance of drawing on diverse sources of knowledge and experiences. By leveraging insights from experts and established evaluation criteria such as the OECD DAC Criteria, stakeholders can enrich their understanding of dialogue outcomes implementation and adapt strategies accordingly. This

reflective approach ensures a robust foundation for assessing the multifaceted aspects of dialogue initiatives and optimizing their impact.

Lastly, the consideration of technology as a facilitator for data collection, analysis, and reporting underscores the potential for leveraging digital tools to streamline processes and enhance collaboration. By measuring the interoperability between different technological platforms and the availability of project management tools, the importance of investing in technology infrastructure is highlighted to support efficient data management and decision-making processes. This technological integration can strengthen the overall monitoring and evaluation framework, enabling stakeholders to track progress more effectively and make informed adjustments as needed.

In conclusion, the reflection on these qualitative indicators underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement, policy influence, sustainability, knowledge exchange, and technological innovation in driving successful dialogue outcomes implementation across the BELLA countries in Latin America. By embracing these insights, stakeholders can enhance their capacity to assess, adapt, and optimize dialogue initiatives for meaningful and lasting impact.

It is important to acknowledge that these indicators may require adaptation and customization to align with the specific context and objectives of the assessment. The findings present an initial collection of generic qualitative metrics that can be further tailored to address the unique requirements of the project. Furthermore, these indicators shed light on the significance of technology in facilitating the gathering, analysis, and reporting of data pertaining to the qualitative indicators employed for evaluating the implementation of dialogue outcomes.

3.1.2. Assessing and monitoring implementation with indicators

The qualitative indicators obtained from a co-creation process based on six questions have the potential to provide a comprehensive and detailed view of the implementation status of dialogue outcomes. These indicators offer a variety of perspectives to understand the effectiveness and impact of ongoing dialogue initiatives.

Given the diversity in the typology of the indicators, their application in SPIDER project activities can vary significantly. For example, in some cases, we might opt to conduct structured interviews or questionnaires to assess stakeholder satisfaction levels or to measure stakeholders' perception and satisfaction regarding the implementation of dialogue outcomes. These tools would provide a detailed understanding of participants' opinions and perceptions, which could directly inform about the impact and effectiveness of dialogue initiatives.

In other cases, we might resort to deeper and more detailed analyses to evaluate the long-term impact of dialogue outcomes. This could involve conducting case studies, analyzing historical data, or tracking progress over time to determine if sustainable changes are being achieved in the specific areas identified by the dialogue.

Furthermore, the selection of the application methodology will also depend on the specific indicator and the context in which the dialogue is being implemented. For example, to assess the quality of dialogue, we could use focus groups or content analysis to better understand the nature and effectiveness of the conversations held during the dialogue process.

In summary, the qualitative indicators offer a wide range of tools and approaches to assess and monitor the implementation of dialogue outcomes. By adapting the application methodology to each specific indicator and relevant context, we can obtain a more comprehensive and detailed understanding of the impact and effectiveness of dialogue initiatives in the EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation.

4. High-level Dialogues of relevance for the EU-LAC digital partnership

4.1. EU – LAC Dialogues on the level of EU – LAC

The following list of dialogues have been identified up to this point. The description of actions highlighted that 8 – 10 dialogues shall be identified. However, this was very quickly overachieved through initial desk research by the SPIDER partner consortium and will likely be even more expansive for the final version of the mapping in month 20:

1. EU-LAC Digital Alliance
 - Dialogue on Cybersecurity
2. EU-LAC High-level Policy Dialogue on digital policy and regulations
3. EU-CELAC STI Senior Officials Meetings since 2010 until since 2011 until 2023 (digital transformation is one of the priority topics under the pillar of global challenges, the bi-regional thematic working group on ICT has been ended)
4. EU-CELAC Joint Initiative on Research and Innovation (JIRI)
5. EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructure (co organised event with RedCLARA in the framework of ResInfra EU-LAC project)
6. EU-LAC Digital Economy Dialogue
7. Taller Cumbre UE-CELAC: Diálogos estratégicos para el desarrollo del ecosistema digital para la educación, la investigación y la innovación de América Latina y el Caribe (17-07-23)
8. BELLA Open Dialogues
 - Dialogue on the Challenges and Opportunities of the Digital Transformation in Latin America and the Caribbean, Montevideo, November 16th, 2022
 - Open dialogue on digital transformation and the role of the higher education institutions. Havana, December 7th, 2022
9. BELLA II Strategic Dialogues
 - Workshop, Panama, November 15th, 2023
10. High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development
11. Fourth meeting of the Conference on Science, Innovation and Information and Communication Technologies of the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean
12. Thirty-ninth session of ECLAC
13. VIII Summit of Heads of State and Government of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC)
14. European Council meeting (21 and 22 March 2024)
15. EU - CELAC Summit
16. EU - CELAC Ministerial meeting
17. Informal meeting of heads of state or government
18. EU-LAC High-Level event on Human Development and Health 2023
19. Dialogue on Sustainable Food Systems- EU - Latin America and the Caribbean Dialogues on Sustainable Food Systems
20. EU-LAC High-level Policy Dialogue on digital policy and regulations
21. Meeting of the European Political Community
22. Summit of Presidents of Mercosur
23. Research Software Funders Forum
24. Community Leaders Forum
25. Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government

The following table describes an initial screening prepared as interim version and also part of the concept note for SPIDER (D1.1).

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development	The HLPF is the central United Nations platform for the follow-up and review of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the global level.	Globally	United Nations	Summary by the President (HLPF 2021) Summary by the President (HLPF 2022) Summary by the President (HLPF 2023)
Fourth meeting of the Conference on Science, Innovation and Information and Communication Technologies of the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean	The Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) views science, technology and innovation as a fundamental enabler of and driving force for the productive transformation needed by the countries of the region to achieve much sought-after sustainable and inclusive development.	LAC	ECLAC	Science, technology and innovation for sustainable and inclusive productive development. Guidelines for 2024-2025
Thirty-ninth session of ECLAC	In a highly complex macroeconomic, social and environmental context in the region that demands a rethinking of short- and long-term public policies, the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) is fulfilling its mandate at its thirty-ninth session, by presenting the countries of the region with a proposal for economic reactivation and transformation of development models in Latin America and the Caribbean.	LAC	ECLAC	Towards transformation of the development model in Latin America and the Caribbean: production, inclusion and sustainability
VIII Summit of Heads of State and Government of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC)	The Heads of State and Government of the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC) met in Kingstown, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines on March 1, 2024, in furtherance their commitment to strengthen integration and give a united voice through consultation, concertation and political dialogue to the multiplicity of challenges, opportunities and strengths facing the region.	LAC	CELAC	DECLARATION OF KINGSTOWN
European Council meeting (21	The European Council held an exchange of views with the UN Secretary-General António	EU	Council of the European Union	European Council meeting (21 and 22

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
and 22 March 2024)	Guterres on the geopolitical situation and key global challenges. The European Council marked the 30th anniversary of the EEA Agreement with the Prime Ministers of Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway			March 2024) - Conclusions
EU-CELAC Summit	<p>The European Union - Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (EU-CELAC) Summit takes place on 17-18 July 2023 in Brussels, Belgium.</p> <p>The third EU-CELAC summit brings EU leaders and leaders from the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC) together. The Summit is co-chaired by Charles MICHEL, President of the European Council; and Ralph GONSALVES, President of CELAC and Prime Minister of Saint Vincent and the Grenadines.</p> <p>The leaders discuss opportunities offered by the green and digital transitions to increase prosperity, with the principles of a fair, social and just transformation central to the talks.</p> <p>During the summit, leaders broach a wide range of topics with a view to further strengthening the EU-CELAC partnership, including: enhanced cooperation in multilateral fora; global peace and stability; trade and investment; economic recovery; efforts to combat climate change; research and innovation; justice and security for citizens.</p>	EU-LAC	Council of the European Union CELAC	Declaration of the EU-CELAC Summit 2023
EU - CELAC Ministerial meeting	Ministers of foreign affairs from the EU and the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States (CELAC) met for the third time on 27 October 2022 in Buenos Aires, holding	EU-LAC	Council of the European Union CELAC	Co-Chairs' Communiqué (press release) CELAC-EU 3rd Foreign Ministers Meeting

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
	discussion around the theme "Renewing the bi-regional partnership to strengthen peace and sustainable development".			Bi-regional roadmap 2022 - 2023
Informal meeting of heads of state or government	EU leaders discussed long-term priorities with regard to enhancing the EU's strategic autonomy. They adopted the Granada declaration, in which they outlined key priorities and actions to make Europe a strong, dynamic and competitive power. The President of the European Council adopted a declaration on migration.	EU	European Union	Declaration by the President of the European Council The Granada declaration
EU-LAC High-Level event on Human Development and Health 2023	Represents an important step in the 2023/2025 EU-CELAC roadmap agreed during the last July's 2023 III EU-CELAC Summit, where Heads of State from both sides of the Atlantic committed to renewing the bi-regional long-standing partnership founded on shared values, interests and strong economic, social and cultural ties.	EU-LAC	Council of the European Union CELAC	
Dialogue on Sustainable Food Systems- EU - Latin America and the Caribbean Dialogues on Sustainable Food Systems	European Union (EU)-Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) Dialogues on Sustainable Food Systems are organised, aiming to promote a constructive exchange of ideas to find common grounds, principles, and initiatives that can pave the way for collaboration to push food systems towards sustainability. These Dialogues are organised with the support of the Foreign Policy Instruments (FPI) and the EU-Lac Policy Dialogue Facility. They will consist of a total of four sub-regional workshops, and concluding with a bi-regional conference expected to take place at the end of 2022	EU-LAC	European Union MERCOSUR	Press Release Policy Dialogues EU - Colombia, Ecuador, Peru on Sustainable Agriculture and Food Systems PRESS RELEASE Building Sustainable Food Systems Together. The European Union, MERCOSUR countries and Chile cooperate towards Sustainable Food Systems for the benefit of farmers, consumers, and the environment. PRESS RELEASE Building Sustainable Food Systems Together. European Union and Central America cooperating

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
				towards Sustainable Food Systems for the benefit of farmers, consumers, and the environment.
EU-LAC High-level Policy Dialogue on digital policy and regulations	It consists of a high-level policy dialogue between the EU and LAC on digital policy and regulation at ministerial and senior official level. The dialogue will help both regions to see the other as a key partner and, by supporting Latin American regional digital integration, build convergence on key policies.	EU-LAC	European Commission	
Meeting of the European Political Community	The European Political Community aims to foster political dialogue and cooperation to address issues of common interest strengthen the security, stability and prosperity of the European continent This platform for political coordination does not replace any existing organisation, structure or process and does not aim to create new ones at this stage.	EU	Council of the European Union	Remarks by President Charles Michel ahead of the second European Political Community meeting (June 2023, October 2023, forthcoming July 2024)
Summit of Presidents of Mercosur	Summit of Heads of State of Mercosur and Associated States and Mercosur and Associated States	LAC	MERCOSUR	Special Declaration of the Presidents of Mercosur on democracy and the integrity of information in digital environments
Research Software Funders Forum	The Research Software Funders Forum is a collaboration of funding organisations committed to supporting research software, and those who develop it, as fundamental and vital to research. It provides a formal mechanism for funders to share practices and consider how to address common challenges to achieve the significant cultural change needed across the research sector globally.	Globally	Research Software Alliance	Research Software Funding Opportunities Research institution policies to support research software - Collection

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
Community Leaders Forum	The Community Leaders Forum (CLF) offers an opportunity for participants to meet other community leaders, engage in interactive discussions, and consider how to address common issues to achieve shared goals. The CLF is one of the online forums that ReSA hosts for decision makers and key influencers in the global research software community.	Globally	Research Software Alliance	Notes of Research Software Community Leaders Forum (CLF)
BELLA II Strategic Dialogues	BELLA II is a regional initiative that aims to reduce the digital divide and support the development of the necessary infrastructure to consolidate and expand a digital ecosystem of science, technology, education, and innovation. It seeks to strengthen and expand the digital ecosystem of Latin America and the Caribbean, enabling relations and exchanges between companies, research centres, educational institutions and national research and education networks, which are aligned with the strategic objectives in education, science, technology and innovation from LAC and Europe.	EU-LAC	Red CLARA	<p>Outcomes Report: BELLA II Strategic Dialogues Workshop</p> <p>Outcomes Report Dialogue on the Challenges and Opportunities of the Digital Transformation in Latin America and the Caribbean</p> <p>o EU-CELAC Summit Workshop: Strategic dialogues for the development of the digital ecosystem for the education, research and innovation in Latin America and the Caribbean</p>
Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government	The Ibero-American Community is advancing in the construction of a roadmap that allows expanding the rights and opportunities of its citizens and finding solutions to the great problems of the region.	Ibero-American States	Ibero-American General Secretariat	<p>Ibero-American Environmental Charter</p> <p>The second is the Ibero-American Charter of Digital Principles and Rights</p> <p>Critical Path to achieve food security</p> <p>Special Communiqué on International Financial Architecture</p>
EU-LAC Digital Alliance Dialogue on Cybersecurity	During the EU-LAC Digital Alliance days in Colombia in November 2023, senior governmental officials and representatives of regional organisations, academia, CSOs and the private sector agreed	EU LAC	D4D HUB	Agenda Digital Alliance cybersecurity dialogue Last update 310124

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
	that collaboration between LAC and EU is essential to enhance global cybersecurity, and contribute to a free, open, safe and secure cyberspace, including by improving capacities to prevent, manage and mitigate cyber-risks.			

4.2. EU – LAC Dialogues outcomes and commitments on the level of EU – LAC

There are various different outcomes and commitments following the dialogues. These include the formats: Action plans, agendas, agreements, charters, communiqués, collections, conclusions, declarations, general plans, guidelines, memorandum of understanding, notes, papers, plans, press releases, remarks, reports, resolutions, roadmaps, summaries, but also more concrete institutional and structural outcomes such as (a whole) accelerator, hub or specific software. To give a better understanding, these are just a few specific examples on very different outcomes and commitments:

- Digital for Development (D4D) Hub in LAC
- Digital Agenda Group Action Plan of MERCOSUR 2023-2025
- EU-CELAC Strategic Roadmap on STI (2021-2023)²
- EU-LAC Digital Accelerator
- EU-LAC Joint Declaration on Digital Alliance
- Roadmap for implementation of EU-CELAC Action Plan on R&I

The following compilation of agreements provide an initial list of the existing landscape pertaining to the advancement of EU-LAC cooperation in the realm of digital transformation. This compilation will be more exhaustive and deepened also towards the final version of the mapping in month 20.

² [New EU-CELAC 2021-2023 Strategic Roadmap to step up research and innovation with the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development	The HLPF is the central United Nations platform for the follow-up and review of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) at the global level.	Globally	United Nations	Ministerial Declaration (HLPF 2021) Ministerial Declaration (HLPF 2022)
Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability	This Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability builds on actions undertaken by the Research Software Alliance (ReSA), research funding organisations, and the community surrounding it to develop awareness about the role funders can play in sustaining software in the longer term.	Globally	Research Software Alliance	Amsterdam Declaration Of Funding Research Software Sustainability Version:0.3 ADORE.software Toolkit
Ibero-American Summit of Heads of State and Government	The Ibero-American Community is advancing in the construction of a roadmap that allows expanding the rights and opportunities of its citizens and finding solutions to the great problems of the region.	Ibero-American States	Ibero-American General Secretariat	III Quadrennial Action Plan of Ibero-American Cooperation (PACCI)
Ministerial Conference on the Information Society in Latin America	The Conference aims to define a set of digital policy priorities at the regional level within the framework of the Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC).	LAC	ECLAC	Montevideo Declaration (2022) Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC2024) Cartagena Declaration (2018) Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC2022)
LXI Summit of Presidents of MERCOSUR	The Presidents of the Argentine Republic, the Republic of Paraguay, the Eastern Republic of Uruguay, the Vice President of the Federative Republic of Brazil, States Parties of MERCOSUR and the High Authorities of the Associated States, meeting in Montevideo, Uruguay, on the occasion of the LXI Summit of Presidents of MERCOSUR, on December 6, 2022.	LAC	MERCOSUR	Special Declaration on Culture of the MERCOSUR States Parties and Associated States Special Declaration on Cybercrime of the MERCOSUR States Parties and Associated States

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
LXIII Summit of Presidents of MERCOSUR	The Presidents of the Argentine Republic, the Federative Republic of Brazil, the Republic of Paraguay, and the Oriental Republic of Uruguay, Member States of MERCOSUR, and the High Authorities of the Associated States, gathered in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, on December 6 and 7, 2023, on the occasion of the LXIII Summit of MERCOSUR Presidents.	LAC	MERCOSUR	Special Declaration of the MERCOSUR Presidents on Democracy and the Integrity of Information in Digital Environments
(RMIS) Reunión de Ministros del Interior y de Seguridad	(RMIS) Reunión de Ministros del Interior y de Seguridad	LAC	MERCOSUR	General Plan of Reciprocal Cooperation and Coordination for Regional Security
Agreement for Cooperation Between Southern Market (MERCOSUR) and the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA)	The objective of the agreement is to establish the general bases of technical cooperation to promote the sustainable development of family agriculture and increase its contribution to food and nutritional security and the rural economy in the MERCOSUR Member States.	LAC	MERCOSUR	Agreement for Cooperation Between Southern Market (MERCOSUR) and the Inter-American Institute for Cooperation on Agriculture (IICA)
Memorandum of Understanding Between Mercosur and the Community of Portuguese Speaking Countries	This Memorandum aims to establish areas and mechanisms of international technical cooperation between the Parties for the development of future actions and/or technical cooperation projects for the benefit of the Member States of both international organisations.	LAC	MERCOSUR CPLP	Memorandum of Understanding Between Mercosur and the Community of Portuguese Speaking Countries
Memorandum of Understanding of International Cooperation between the Common Market of the South (MERCOSUR) and the Development Bank of Latin America and	The objective of this Memorandum seeks the development of actions, projects, and cooperation programs with a focus on sustainable human development that allows improving the standard of living, strengthening social and productive structures of excluded communities in the region, and promoting the exchange of good practices and successful public policies that contribute to social inclusion.	LAC	MERCOSUR CAF	Memorandum of Understanding of International Cooperation between the Common Market of the South (MERCOSUR) and the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF).

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
the Caribbean (CAF)				
Memorandum of Understanding between Mercosur and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture	Memorandum of Understanding between Mercosur and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture	LAC Ibero-American States	MERCOSUR OEI	Memorandum of Understanding between Mercosur and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture
Cooperation Mechanism between National Data Protection Authorities for Mutual Assistance and Technical, Regulatory and Supervisory Cooperation on the Protection of Personal Data within the framework of MERCOSUR	The purpose of this Mechanism is to establish instances so that national authorities in data protection can make the necessary efforts to promote mutual assistance and technical, regulatory and supervisory cooperation in matters of privacy and personal data protection	LAC	MERCOSUR	Cooperation Mechanism between National Data Protection Authorities for Mutual Assistance and Technical, Regulatory and Supervisory Cooperation on the Protection of Personal Data within the framework of MERCOSUR
Digital Agenda Group Action Plan 2023-2025	The Action Plan of the Digital Agenda Group (GAD) of MERCOSUR aims to be an instrument that allows unifying different priority initiatives of the Group in the same roadmap that favour the development of the block's digital policy, these being driven by the coordinated work of specific technical commissions or by different specialised subgroups, on relevant topics such as: the development of digital infrastructure and connectivity in the region; the increase of cross-border trade and the regional digital market; the increase in security in the digital environment; digital signature, digital government; improvement in the measurement of access and use of ICT; the promotion of digital inclusion in the block; and coordination in regulatory	LAC	MERCOSUR	Digital Agenda Group Action Plan 2023-2025

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
	aspects and in international forums on agenda topics			
TTC Joint Roadmap for Trustworthy AI and Risk Management	The EU-US Trade and Technology Council TTC Joint Roadmap aims to advance shared terminologies and taxonomies, but also to inform our approaches to AI risk management and trustworthy AI on both sides of the Atlantic	EU US	European Commission	TTC Joint Roadmap on Evaluation and Measurement Tools for Trustworthy AI and Risk Management 1 December 2022 EU-U.S. Terminology and Taxonomy for Artificial Intelligence - Second Edition
Regulation on the adoption of a European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme	The European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) builds on the Mutual Recognition Agreement ('MRA') of Information Technology Security Certificates of the Senior Officials Group Information Systems Security ('SOG-IS') using the Common Criteria, including the group's procedures and documents.	EU	European Commission	1. Implementing Regulation on the adoption of a European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme 2. Annex to the Implementing Regulation on the adoption of a European Common Criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme
The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) is a legal and funding entity, created in 2018 and located in Luxembourg. The EuroHPC JU achieved autonomy in September 2020. The EuroHPC Joint Undertaking allows the European Union and EuroHPC participating countries to coordinate their efforts and pool their resources with the objective of making Europe a world leader in high performance computing (HPC).	EU	European Commission	The European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
European Declaration on Quantum Technologies	The signatory Member States recognise the strategic importance of quantum technologies for the scientific and industrial competitiveness of the EU and commit to collaborating on the development of a world-class quantum technology ecosystem across Europe, with the ultimate aim of making Europe the 'quantum valley' of the world, the leading region globally for quantum excellence and innovation	EU	European Commission	European Declaration on Quantum Technologies
Advancing 6G: A Vision for Transatlantic Collaboration	Through the Trade and Technology Council (TTC), the U.S. and EU have a unique opportunity to foster collaboration in research and innovation, ensuring that the development and deployment of 6G technology align with shared principles and values.	EU US	European Commission	U.S.-EU Trade and Technology Council (TTC) - Advancing 6G: A Vision for Transatlantic Collaboration
First Latin American and Caribbean Ministerial and High Level Summit on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence (2023)	<p>With the support of CAF and UNESCO, Chile received ministers and high-level authorities from more than 30 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean in an unprecedented meeting in the region.</p> <p>The Ministers and High Authorities representing the countries of Latin America and the Caribbean, gathered in Santiago de Chile on October 23 and 24, 2023, on the occasion of the Forum on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence in Latin America and the Caribbean, and the Ministerial Summit and High Authorities of Latin America and the Caribbean, which seeks to facilitate the exchange of impressions regarding the challenges and opportunities of the development of artificial intelligence (AI) in the region and discuss ways to address them, including the establishment of a Working Group with a view to the constitution of an Intergovernmental Council of Artificial Intelligence for Latin America and the Caribbean.</p>	LAC	UNESCO CAF	Santiago Declaration

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
<p>Decision (EU) 2022/2481 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030</p>	<p>This Decision establishes the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 and sets out a monitoring and cooperation mechanism for that programme designated to:</p> <p>(a) creating an environment favourable to innovation and investment by setting a clear direction for the digital transformation of the Union and for the delivery of digital targets at Union level by 2030, on the basis of measurable indicators;</p> <p>(b) structuring and stimulating cooperation between the European Parliament, the Council, the Commission and the Member States;</p> <p>(c) fostering the consistency, comparability, transparency and completeness of monitoring and reporting by the Union.</p> <p>2. This Decision establishes a framework for multi-country projects.</p>	<p>EU</p>	<p>European Parliament Council of the European Union</p>	<p>Decision (EU) 2022/2481 Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030</p>
<p>Decisions: Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU</p>	<p>This Decision establishes the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (the 'Specific Programme'), as set out in point (a) of Article 1(2) of Regulation (EU) 2021/695.</p> <p>This Decision lays down the operational objectives of the Specific Programme, the budget for the period 2021-2027, the rules for implementation of the Specific Programme and the activities to be carried out under the Specific Programme.</p>	<p>EU</p>	<p>Council of the European Union</p>	<p>Decisions: Council Decision (EU) 2021/764 of 10 May 2021 establishing the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, and repealing Decision 2013/743/EU</p> <p>COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION of 20.3.2024 on adopting the 2025-2027 strategic research and innovation plan under the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe – The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation</p>

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
				ANNEX: Commission Implementing Decision adopting the 2025-2027 research and innovation strategic plan under the Specific Programme implementing Horizon Europe - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
EuroLat Resolution: on international cooperation and multilateralism in a COVID-19 context	EUROLAT – Resolution of 27 July – Madrid based on the report by the Committee on Political Affairs, Security and Human Rights on international cooperation and multilateralism in a COVID-19 context	EU-LAC	EURO-LATIN AMERICAN PARLIAMENTARY ASSEMBLY	EuroLat Resolution on international cooperation and multilateralism in a COVID-19 context
EuroLat Resolution: on Bi-regional cooperation for the strengthening of health systems, for access to and distribution of vaccines, and for scientific research to face pandemics	EUROLAT – Resolution of 27 July 2023 – Madrid based on the report by the Committee on Social Affairs, Youth and Children, Human Exchanges, Education and Culture Bi-regional cooperation for the strengthening of health systems, for access to and distribution of vaccines, and for scientific research to face pandemics	EU-LAC	EURO-LATIN AMERICAN PARLIAMENTARY ASSEMBLY	EuroLat Resolution: on Bi-regional cooperation for the strengthening of health systems, for access to and distribution of vaccines, and for scientific research to face pandemics
EU-Latin America and Caribbean Digital Alliance	EU-LAC Digital Alliance creates a strategic framework to foster substantial bi-regional cooperation across the full spectrum of digital and space issues. The Alliance's aim is to foster the development of secure, resilient and human-centric digital infrastructures on the basis of a values-based framework, ensuring a democratic and transparent enabling environment and putting a strong emphasis on privacy and digital rights. It is the first intercontinental digital partnership agreed between both regions under Global Gateway investment strategy, the EU's offer for	EU CELAC	European Commission	EU-Latin America and Caribbean Digital Alliance EU 2030 Digital Compass EU-LAC Digital Accelerator Expanding the BELLA programme

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
	trusted and sustainable connections with partner countries.			Establishing a regional Copernicus strategy
Conference on the Future of Europe	The Conference on the Future of Europe was launched in March 2021 as a joint undertaking of the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the European Commission, to listen to European citizens and let them have their say on the future of Europe, through a citizen-led series of debates and deliberations. The focus is now on the follow-up.	EU	Council of the European Union	Putting Vision into Concrete Action (2022) Commission work programme 2023 Conference on the Future of Europe - Proposals and related specific measures contained in the report on the final outcome of the Conference on the Future of Europe: Updated assessment
CAF Chile Country Strategy 2023-2026	Since Chile's reintegration into CAF, one of the most notable news of the last 20 years of the bank, CAF's programmatic work in the country has focused on becoming a relevant actor for its sustainable and balanced development. To this end, it has strived to generate spaces for exchange and technical dialogue backed by the support of CAF's specialised areas, showing various actors, public and private, its experience and timely and relevant response capacity to contribute to the development agenda driven by the Government of Chile	LAC	CAF	CAF Chile Country Strategy 2023-2026
CAF Colombia Country Strategy 2023-2026	Since its founding in 1968, CAF, the development bank of Latin America and the Caribbean, has supported Colombia by financing large-scale programs and projects, and strengthening technical and regulatory capacities for the implementation of high-impact public policies.	LAC	CAF	CAF Colombia Country Strategy 2023-2026

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
Partnership for Development in Latin America and the Caribbean	CAF -the development bank of Latin America and the Caribbean- and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) have signed a framework agreement on procedures that will allow both institutions to collaborate more agilely in generating knowledge, providing technical assistance, and financing instruments to offer comprehensive solutions with local impact in alignment with the national development priorities of the countries in the region.	LAC	CAF UNDP	Framework Agreement CAF-UNDP
Partnership for Development in Latin America and the Caribbean	The Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) reaffirmed their long-standing cooperation through a new framework agreement to foster enhanced collaboration through harmonising operational and procurement processes for more efficient cooperation and accelerating sustainable development in Latin America and the Caribbean.	LAC	IDB UNDP	Framework Agreement IDB-UNDP
GovTech Global Partnership	To support countries in adopting sound practices and solutions in GovTech, and to ensure a broad global partnership for effective exchange and transfer of knowledge and good practice, the GovTech Global Partnership (GTGP) was first established by the World Bank's Governance Global Practice partnership with the Government of Switzerland, Austria, and Korea in 2019. The GTGP is a multi-stakeholder initiative that includes advanced and aspiring GovTech countries, development partners, private sector, academia, civil society, and others involved in the GovTech domain.	Globally	WORLD BANK CAF Ministries (Korea, Austria, Switzerland)	GovTech Partnership Global

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
EU Policy and Outreach Partnership in South America	The main goal of this project consists in supporting the achievement of EU Foreign Policy objectives by implementation by strengthening the EU's ability to engage with different audiences and stakeholders in third countries through Public Diplomacy. In this sense, it expects to further develop the EU's soft power by enhancing widespread understanding and visibility of the EU and its role on the world scene, through public diplomacy and outreach activities on issues relevant to the bilateral relations specifically with Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Peru and possibly other countries in South America.	EU-LAC	OEI European Union	EU Policy and Outreach Partnership in South America
Framework agreement OEI-EU-CELAC Foundation	Framework agreement establishing the bases of cooperation for the development of programmes and activities of mutual interest, especially in the areas of education, science, culture and research.	Ibero-American States EU	OEI EU-LAC Foundation	Framework agreement OEI-EU-CELAC Foundation
Program for the Strengthening of Science and Technology Systems (FORCYT)	FORCYT is an initiative of the Organization of Ibero-American States (OEI) and the European Union (EU), co-financed by the EU's Transition Development Facility	EU-LAC	OEI European Union	
Cooperation Agreement	CAF, Development Bank of Latin America, and the Organization of Ibero-American States for Education, Science and Culture (OEI) signed a non-reimbursable technical cooperation agreement on Thursday to support the Project for the Promotion and Articulation of Innovation Ecosystems in Latin America	LAC	OEI CAF	Cooperation Agreement OEI - CAF

Name	Description	Region of Impact	Main actors	Main Outcomes
Global Gateway in Latin America and the Caribbean	<p>Global Gateway projects are developed and delivered jointly by Team Europe, which consists of the EU institutions, Member States, European financial institutions working together with European businesses, governments, civil society and the private sector in partner countries.</p> <p>Global Gateway seeks to create a partnership where the public sector of Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean link up with the private sector to generate business investments to contribute to wealthier societies to the benefit of all.</p>	EU-LAC	European Commission	EU-LAC Gateway Agenda Global Investment
Collaboration agreement to jointly deepen bi-regional relations between Latin America, the Caribbean and Europe	<p>For both SEGIB and the EU-LAC Foundation, committed to multilateral interaction and collaboration, the signing of this agreement is an excellent opportunity to bring the two regions closer together through a range of instruments and joint activities ranging from the organisation and implementation of conferences, seminars and workshops to the production of publications and information relevant to the bi-regional partnership in 2022.</p>	Ibero-American States EU	SEGIB EU-LAC Foundation	Joint press release from the EU-LAC International Foundation and the Ibero-American General Secretariat (SEGIB)
Joint Declaration on a partnership between the States Parties to the Framework Agreement of the Pacific Alliance and the European Union	<p>Enhance social, productive and lasting ties, based on the principles of democracy, human rights and rule of law, and a shared vision on open trade and investment, and sustainable development</p>	EU-LAC	EU AP (Pacific Alliance)	Joint Declaration on a partnership between the States Parties to the Framework Agreement of the Pacific Alliance and the European Union
Joint Declaration Pacific Alliance - OECD	<p>Establish solid, productive, strategic and longstanding ties, strengthening cooperation between the Participants based on a shared vision of the benefits of multilateral cooperation, economic integration, the exchange of best practices and the promotion and implementation of OECD standards.</p>	LAC	AP (Pacific Alliance)	Joint Declaration Pacific Alliance - OECD

4.3. Dialogues on the level of EU and bilateral countries

There are, in addition, various dialogues that are focusing more on the EU level, the EU Member States or Associated Countries level and specific bilateral countries in Latin America and/or the Caribbean. Examples for this interim version are listed here (not at all exhaustive):

- Argentina
 - Argentina Digital Agenda 2030
- Brazil International Digital Dialogues
 - EU -Brazilian Digital Dialogue (March 2024)³: On 20 March, the European Union and the Government of Brazil held their 12th Digital Dialogue in Brasilia, Brazil. At the occasion of the Digital dialogue, the EU and Brazil agreed to cooperate on connectivity projects, particularly in under-served regions of Brazil, continue their common work on 5G and 6G technologies and support enhanced cooperation between High Performance Computing centres in Brazil and the EU. Moreover, both partners also aim to foster exchange of information on semiconductors supply chains, work on the technical interoperability of digital signature systems, continue the dialogue on data protection and international data flows and exchange best practices and promote cooperation on the regulatory frameworks for data, artificial intelligence and platforms. They will continue to cooperate in international fora based on their shared values. The European Union and Brazil issued a joint communiqué. The next Digital Dialogue is planned for 2025.
 - Brazilian - German Digital Dialogue (March 2021)⁴: The German Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport (BMDV) and the Brazilian Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MCTI) conduct a bilateral Digital Dialogue. Within this Digital Dialogue, they implement activities to support the digital transformation of small and medium-sized enterprises, as well as strategy-building initiatives in the areas of internet governance, data protection, Industrie 4.0, artificial intelligence (AI), industrial 5G applications and cybersecurity.
- Mexico International Digital Dialogues
 - Mexican – German Digital Dialogue (September 2022)⁵: A Work Plan for the bilateral Digital Dialogue was signed in September 2022. It focuses on three main pillars: (1) Innovation and technology transfer, (2) Data policy, and (3) Emerging technologies and Industrie 4.0.
- Chile
 - Digital Chile Digital 2020
- Costa Rica
 - Programa Fortaleciendo sistemas inclusivos de ciencia e innovación en América Latina a través de una red de investigación colaborativa IDRC
 - BID funding program
 - CAF funding program
 - Plan Nacional De Ciencia, Tecnología E Innovación 2022-2027
 - Plan Nacional de Desarrollo e Inversión Pública 2023-2026 de Costa Rica
- Panama
 - BELLA II Diálogo Estratégico de Panamá en el marco de la Conferencia TICAL 2023 (15-11-23)
- Dominican Republic
 - In 2021, the Dominican Republic co-organized the EU-LAC High-Level Political Dialogue on Cybersecurity, held in Santo Domingo. This dialogue

³ [The EU and Brazil strengthen their digital cooperation | Shaping Europe's digital future \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁴ [Brazil - Digital Dialogues \(digital-dialogues.net\)](#)

⁵ [Mexico - Digital Dialogues \(digital-dialogues.net\)](#)

brought together high-level representatives from the European Union, Latin America and the Caribbean to discuss the challenges and opportunities of cybersecurity in the region.

- In 2022, the Dominican Republic participated in the EU-LAC Regional Dialogue on Artificial Intelligence, held in Buenos Aires, Argentina. This dialogue addressed the potential of artificial intelligence for the sustainable development of the region.
- In 2023, the Dominican Republic is participating in the EU-LAC Regional Dialogue on Digital Transformation, which is being held in Brussels, Belgium. This dialogue focuses on identifying areas of cooperation to promote digital transformation in the region.

4.4. Multilateral Dialogues on a multilateral level

- Pacific Alliance
 - On September 26 and 27, the Pacific Alliance, through the Subcommittee on Digital Economy (SCED), held the “Workshop on Business Digital Security and private transactions”, in the framework of the implementation of the Regional Digital Market Roadmap.⁶
- Mercosur Digital
 - Mercosur Agenda Digital
 - Fueling Digital Trade in Mercosur: A Regulatory Roadmap
- United Nations
 - UN Internet Governance Forum 2021⁷: The 16th annual IGF meeting was hosted by the Government of Poland in Katowice from 6-10 December, under the overarching theme: Internet United.
 - Digital Agenda for LAC (2024)⁸ : The Digital Agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean (eLAC) is a strategy aimed at 2024, which promotes the use of digital technologies as instruments for sustainable development. Its mission is to encourage the development of the digital ecosystem in Latin America and the Caribbean through a process of integration and regional cooperation, strengthening digital policies that drive knowledge, inclusion and equality, innovation and environmental sustainability.

5. Analysis

The outcoming agreements have been analyzed in order to

- identify the most important actors and main drivers to enhance EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation and to approach them e.g. for the survey on connecting to BELLA
- bi-regional thematic priorities related to digital transformation technologies
- practical applications resulting from the dialogues, e.g. EU-LAC Digital Accelerator
- find out about resulting commitments, e.g. such as further dialogues or funding programmes etc.

⁶ [The Pacific Alliance promotes dialogue between public and private actors to foster business digital security – Alianza del Pacífico. \(alianzapacifico.net\)](https://alianzapacifico.net)

⁷ [IGF 2021 | Internet Governance Forum \(intgovforum.org\)](https://intgovforum.org)

⁸ [Digital agenda for Latin America and the Caribbean \(eLAC2024\) | CEPAL](https://cepal.org)

5.1. Exemplary analysis of commitments and agreements resulting from the dialogues

As examples for deeper analysis of the dialogues and their commitments, the EU – LAC Digital Alliance in general, the EU-LAC Digital Alliance Days in Cartagena de Indias, Colombia and the MERCOSUR Digital Trade Roadmap have been analysed in an exemplary style:

5.1.1. EU – LAC Digital Alliance

Characteristics

The European Union (EU) and Argentina, The Bahamas, Barbados, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, the Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Jamaica, Mexico, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, and Uruguay have agreed to deepen their partnership by establishing an EU-LAC Digital Alliance.

It was endorsed by a Joint Declaration at the third EU-CELAC Summit in July 2023.

The partners of the Alliance will meet regularly at different levels, including a periodic High-Level Policy Dialogue, regulatory dialogue and other meetings at technical level as appropriate. These meetings will serve for a free exchange of information and the identification of joint priorities. A progress review will take place on an annual basis.

Actors:

The EU participates as Team Europe with Member States and their development agencies, European financial institutions and the LAC branch of the Digital4Development Hub. The Alliance will also provide for the participation of other stakeholders, such as the private sector, research and academic networks, and other social actors from both regions, as appropriate.

Main themes:

Wide range of digital issues:

including digital policy dialogue, internet governance, data governance, infrastructure, connectivity, security, data protection, artificial intelligence and other new emerging digital technologies, skills development, technology, entrepreneurship and innovation, digital trade, and space-related activities such as Copernicus Earth observation data and Galileo/EGNOS satellite navigation applications and services. Knowledge transfer and exchange on digital citizenship, digitisation of public services and registries, digital identity, electronic signatures and related interoperability will also be pursued.

Practical applications:

Connections shall be made with EU-supported infrastructure in the LAC region, like:

- the BELLA programme
- Copernicus Centres
- the LAC Cyber Competence Centre
- the Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency (ALCE)

Figure 5 Joint Declaration

- Other specific projects, for example on cybercrime under the EL PACCTO programme.

Resulting commitments:

- **High Level Policy Dialogues**
- **Investment Agenda**, which are to be agreed upon by the two regions
- A number of **Global Gateway flagship initiatives**. In 2023, cooperation will include the following activities, among others:
 - a) the extension of the BELLA fibre-optic cable to interested countries, building secure digital backbone connectivity and bringing the research communities of the EU and LAC closer together
 - b) the implementation of a regional Copernicus Strategy including two regional Copernicus data centres in Panama and Chile; and
 - c) the establishment of an EU-LAC Digital Accelerator aiming to foster multi-stakeholder collaboration between EU and LAC corporations, SMEs and innovative start-ups. The objective is to facilitate and accelerate at least 40 joint ventures for bi-regional innovation and digital transformation.

Link: [EU – LAC Digital Alliance](#)

5.1.2. EU-LAC Digital Alliance Days

Characteristics

Over 150 senior government representatives from Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), the European Union (EU) and its Member States, as well as civil society, academia, and private sector, gathered in Cartagena de Indias, Colombia, on 27-29 November 2023, with the purpose of identifying concrete areas to advance digital cooperation towards the next EU-CELAC Summit, to be held in Colombia in 2025.

The EU-LAC Digital Alliance Days underlined the political determination of the partner countries to collaborate closely on key digital matters through shared dialogue and joint initiatives, fostering a human-centric digital transformation in both regions. As a critical component to delivering the ambitions of the Global Gateway in Latin America and the Caribbean, it forms part of the EU offer to build and boost trusted and sustainable connections with partner countries.

Actors:

Co-organized by the European Commission, the Spanish Agency for International Development (AECID), the Digital for Development (D4D) Hub, and key partners of the EU-LAC Digital Alliance, brought together over 150 senior government representatives from Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), the European Union (EU) and its Member States, as well as civil society, academia, and private sector, such as AECID Training Center. Co-financed by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ).

Figure 6 Web-Article on the EU-LAC Digital Alliance Days (website German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ))

Main themes

Artificial Intelligence (AI), data governance, digital government, inclusive connectivity, and cybersecurity

Practical Applications

None so far

Resulting Commitments

The EU-LAC Digital Alliance Days underlined the political determination of the partner countries to collaborate closely on key digital matters through shared dialogue and joint initiatives, fostering a human-centric digital transformation in both regions. In this context, the event marked an important milestone in the strengthening of the bi-regional digital partnership following the endorsement of a Joint Declaration at the third EU-CELAC Summit in July 2023 towards the next EU-CELAC Summit, to be held in Colombia in 2025. Moreover, a first follow-up dialogue on cybersecurity in February 2024 was hosted by the Dominican Republic, with follow-up dialogues on connectivity and digital inclusion, data governance and e-governance taking place later in the year.

Link: [Recap: EU-LAC Digital Alliance Days in Colombia – Partners Agree on Joint Areas of Collaboration Towards 2025 Summit | BMZ Digital.Global \(bmz-digital.global\)](https://bmz-digital.global)

5.1.3. MERCOSUR Digital

Characteristics

Fueling Digital Trade in Mercosur: A Regulatory Roadmap (2018)

The purpose of this report is to provide a regulatory roadmap that helps Mercosur region’s policymakers and business leaders in this key juncture to unlock digital trade in goods and services as an engine of regional trade and job-creation. The report pays particular attention to frameworks and policies that enable Mercosur region governments best help SMEs that sell goods and services online to grow, export, and create jobs. This report draws on new interview and survey data on the way firms in the region leverage ecommerce, and on the enabling environment for ecommerce, and puts forth policy recommendations.

Actors: Mercado Común del Sur (MERCOSUR) countries, Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) region, Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), Mercosur Region’s Online and Digital Companies such as FinTechs, EdTechs, AgTechs, examples on p.10 and throughout the report.

Main Themes: FinTechs, EdTechs, AgTechs, digital trade, blockchain, machine learning, eTrader, Ecommerce, regulatory practices, digital regulations, small businesses, technology start-ups, intellectual property (IP) rights and protections, over-the-top (OTT) rules⁹, fixed broadband, mobile broadband, data protection and privatization, Internet intermediary liability, Taxes on digital companies, Internet Exchange Points (IXPs)

⁹ OTT (over-the-top) is a means of providing television and film content over the internet at the request and to suit the requirements of the individual consumer. The term itself stands for “over-the-top”, which implies that a content provider is going over the top of existing internet services. <https://www.telestream.net/video/solutions/what-is-ott.htm> , accessed 30.04.2024

Practical Applications:

- The report lists several experiences from around the world for a digital integration and names the following that could be relevant to draw lessons learned from for SPIDER and EU-LAC Digital agendas or roadmaps:
 - The Pacific Alliance Digital Agenda (2016) pledging to work in 2017 toward regional digital market, regional cybersecurity, and public - private dialogues on the digital economy
 - European Union's Digital Single Market: In May 2015, the European Commission unveiled its plan to create a Digital Single Market aimed to tear down national regulatory silos by the end of 2016 through (1) improved access for consumers and businesses to digital goods and services across Europe; (2) a level playing field for digital networks and innovative services to flourish; (3) maximized the growth potential of the digital economy. The EU has also enabled online content portability, allowing EU citizens to access online subscription services while traveling within the EU – thereby ending the so - called “geo - blocking” tactics.
 - ASEAN ICT Master Plan. The ASEAN ICT Masterplan 2020 focuses on fuelling digital transformation of traditional industries and building a single integrated market for digital economy. It follows a Masterplan 2015 that was more about digital infrastructures and human capital for digital industries. ASEAN legislation has especially focused on electronic transactions, cybercrime, consumer protection, content regulation, data protection and privacy, domain names, and dispute resolution.
 - APEC's Electronic Commerce Steering Group (ECSG). APEC's ECSG promotes the development and use of e - commerce through legal, regulatory, and policy environments in the APEC region that are predictable, transparent, and consistent. The ECSG also explores how ICTs can drive economic growth and social development and has guided numerous capacity - building projects promoting the development and use of ecommerce and ICTs in the APEC region.
 - The APEC Data Privacy Pathfinder and Subgroup. In 2007, APEC ministers endorsed the APEC Data Privacy Pathfinder initiative aimed to achieve cross - border flow of personal information within the Asia - Pacific region. APEC also has in place a Data Privacy Subgroup that helps identify best practices and build member economies' capacity for data protection and promote common data privacy approaches across the APEC region, and oversee the CBPR's functioning. In August 2017, ECSG's Data Privacy Subgroup met with the European Commission to discuss interoperability on data protection and transfer between the CBPR and GDPR
- Mainly in the area of Fin Tech, MERCOSUR countries try modernising customs procedures to facilitate and secure new trade with new data - driven “Trusted eTrader” program and the use of blockchain and machine learning (p.6)
- The report hinted that taking a step further, the regional governments could draw on UK's work in FinTech regulations and establish a regional regulatory “sandbox” where companies in the Mercosur region could introduce digital innovations to any one Mercosur market or all Mercosur markets without requiring full regulatory approvals, and regulators could proceed learn how the innovation is used in the marketplace and establish regulations where they may be beneficial. This type of “learning by doing” takes guesswork and costly errors from the process of fashioning domestic and regional digital regulations (p.7)

Resulting Commitments

The report encourages Mercosur countries to promote the region's economic potential through digitisation by:

1. Creating smart digital regulations, and enforcing them in a pragmatic manner;

2. Driving at mutual recognition of online service providers;
3. Modernising customs procedures to facilitate and secure new trade;
4. Creating new instruments to fund SME skills development;
5. Starting systematic 'Regional Digital Dialogues'. Mercosur governments agreed to establish a **Digital Dialogue** (Dialogo Digital) that brings together each quarter government officials with businesses and consumer groups to discuss the benefits of new technologies and optimal regulatory frameworks for them and learn from best regulatory practices from other regions and world - class researchers (p7). The dialogues should result in:
 - o Concrete regulatory roadmaps and implementation schedules;
 - o Plan for metrics and analytics to monitor of the impact of regulations once they are in place, based on business and consumer surveys, case studies and interviews, and rigorous econometric analyses;
 - o Metrics and analytics to track SMEs' digital trade and their skills for doing cross - border ecommerce;
 - o An online platform to track the implementation regulations and is available publicly, as in Chile's Digital Chile Digital 2020 website that tracks the implementation of over 60 measures impacting the digital economy;
 - o Rigorous, data - driven assessments of the interoperability of domestic digital regulations with Mercosur markets, so that digital companies and online sellers grow and scale in the broader intra - regional market.
 - o Concrete plan to improve data and measurements of the digital economy, so as to help track policies, motivate policy improvements, and craft appropriate policies to facilitate digital trade. Innovative censuses and surveys can bolster official statistics, while public - private partnerships can leverage the rich real - time data that private sector has to assess the state of the regional digital economy.

Link: <https://publications.iadb.org/en/publications/english/viewer/Fueling-Digital-Trade-in-Mercosur-A-Regulatory-Roadmap.pdf>

5.1.4. Statement on reinforcing and converging digital policy and regulatory frameworks on AI

Characteristics

On July 17th 2023, the EU and Argentina, The Bahamas, Barbados, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, the Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Jamaica, Mexico, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, and Uruguay signed a joint declaration on a Digital Alliance, an informal, values-based framework for cooperation. It is open to all Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) countries and EU Member States who may participate through their respective governments and agencies related to the digital agenda.

Actors: EU and Argentina, The Bahamas, Barbados, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, the Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Jamaica, Mexico, Panama,

Figure 7 Statement on reinforcing and converging digital policy and regulatory frameworks on AI

Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, and Uruguay, UNESCO, EU – LAC Digital Alliance, Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU, Council of the EU

Main themes: AI, digital policy, regulatory frameworks, linguistics, responsible and inclusive AI practices, innovative and trustworthy AI and accelerators, human rights

Practical Applications

A bi-regional investment package exists for the implementation of the Digital Alliance.

Resulting Commitments

In the EU, the upcoming Regulation on AI will define a set of requirements based on risks to safety and fundamental rights that will have to be complied with by providers of AI systems. The Regulation on AI also foresees the creation of regulatory sandboxes to enable development and testing of innovative AI systems in a controlled environment and under the supervision of competent authorities.

This includes:

1. Exchanging best practices on AI regulation.
 - States will promote the exchange of best practices and sharing of operational regulatory measures and guidelines, including on the governance mechanisms set up to implement and monitor AI regulation. In the case of EU countries, this shall fall under the scope of the Regulation on AI and the Coordinated Plan on AI.
 - Foster an environment where AI development thrives across linguistic diversities, particularly in Spanish, Portuguese and other official languages of the EU, to ensure AI technologies cater to the unique needs and contexts of the different communities, fostering innovation and inclusivity on a linguistic level.
 - States may take into account the work on ethical guidelines outlined by UNESCO, particularly nations in Latin America and the Caribbean. These guidelines encompass a collective commitment to fostering responsible and inclusive AI practices.
2. Implementing convergence on policy and regulatory frameworks on AI.
 - A bi-regional investment package exists for the implementation of the Digital Alliance. States will jointly define the form of Digital Alliance investment to be allocated for the purposes of this statement. Having under consideration local contexts and different needs and opportunities that States may have.
3. Maintaining a regular dialogue to exchange information with a view to converging digital policy and regulatory frameworks on AI, while ensuring that innovation, human capital and infrastructure are fostered, and human rights are respected.
 - Regular dialogue will encourage the development of AI regulation that fosters innovation, human capital and infrastructure while ensuring safety, and protects human rights. These states will consider the different paces and impacts that the development of AI has taken in each individual country.
 - Within these dialogues, States will have under their consideration the development of legislation and, as a possibility, sandboxes for innovative and trustworthy AI and accelerators, and to share good practices and lessons learnt in this respect, in particular to help innovative startups and SMEs to create trustworthy AI.

Link [171123-Statement on AI EU LAC Final.pdf \(lamoncloa.gob.es\)](#)

5.2. Main Actors involved on digital dialogues and agreements

5.2.1. Stakeholders identified through the Co-creation Workshop 14th December 2023

On December 14th, 2023, the inaugural SPIDER online workshop was conducted with the following objectives to (1) facilitate a brainstorming session focused on identifying the necessary measures to enhance EU-LAC cooperation in the realm of digital transformation and (2) to promote collaboration and teamwork among participants. A Miro board was utilised as a collaborative tool for brainstorming including a dedicated section on main actors and stakeholders. The overall results found entry in Task 1.1 (D1.1) - Concept note for EU-LAC cooperation on digital transformation. The workshop was attended by 19 members representing various partner institutions within the SPIDER consortium. The meeting was conducted via a 2-hour Zoom session.

For a visual representation of the workshop outputs, the following Figure illustrates the Miro boards that were put available online.

Figure 8 Miro board of the SPIDER Co-Creation Workshop

The following main actors in a very general way were identified through the Miro exercise, and included Regional and National Research and Education Networks, RedCLARA, the BELLA network, GEANT Community, Research performing Organisation (RPOs), Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), LAC space agencies, Policy makers, ICT and digital dialogues leaders, Digital and ICT companies, Civil society organizations, Society at large.

Categories	Ideas
Actors	Universities
Actors	LAC Space agencies
Actors	Funders
Actors	Digital Innovation Hubs
Actors	Researchers
Actors	Governments
Actors	Incubators
Actors	IT Corporates
Actors	NRENS
Actors	Industry
Actors	KICs from EIT (EIT Digital)
Actors	Policy level representatives, EU Delegations in LAC, DG Regio
Actors	Researchers and Universities
Actors	Specific "thematic" communities that are already connected EU-LAC, like for AI, Big Data, Blockchain etc.
Actors	RENS
Actors	Private sector intermediaries and companies
Actors	EU-LAC Foundation
Actors	Bilateral projects
Actors	Ministries that hold responsibility for Digital Agendas/Policies in EU and LAC (federal, state, national level)
Actors	R&I
Actors	NRENS
Actors	Industry
Actors	Public Institutions
Actors	CELAC pro-tempore presidency
Actors	Multilateral organisms
Actors	European Commission (DG CONNECT, DG INTPA)
Actors	STI Ministries, Industry + Teleco + funding agencies
Actors	CEPAL, LACNIC
Actors	All the actors can work and relate together.
Actors	Non-governmental Institutions
Actors	Academia
Actors	Telecommunications Companies
Actors	Computer Science, R&I in computing, AI, etc.
Actors	Universities and RTOs
Actors	Organizations in terms of digital education

Figure 9 Actors identified through the Miro exercise

The main actors from an initial review also encompass e.g. European Union, MERCOSUR countries, Inter Development Bank, Research Software Alliance and many more. See column under section 4.1. This list needs to be expanded to fully identify more actors specifically.

5.3. Main themes

The main themes of the SPIDER project as mentioned in the description of action include AI, 5G, Blockchain, Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity and Virtual Research Environments (VRE). Through the first initial workshop this was already expanded by further keywords such as digital transformation or quantum technologies.

Categories	Ideas
New categories	Digital transformation X Digital Transition?
New categories	Identify and connect with key people.
New categories	Blockchain
New categories	Human-centric approach
New categories	Security
New categories	Quantum Technologies
New categories	Digital Twins - abstract concept that we could explore and could be included in some dialogues.
New categories	Human-centred research-innovation

New categories	Platform for visualization of actors in the R&I ecosystem
New categories	HPC
New categories	IA
New categories	Intra and bi-regional collaboration strategies defined.
New categories	Common Framework/Strategy for LAC and EU
New categories	Quantum technologies
New categories	Digital Transformation or Digital Transition?

Figure 10 Main themes mentioned during the workshop

The exemplary analysis of e.g. the digital alliance included also mostly Artificial Intelligence (AI), data governance, digital government, inclusive connectivity, and cybersecurity.

5.4. Practical applications of EU-LAC digital dialogue’s commitments

The practical applications resulting from the digital dialogues range from Software platforms to accelerators and hubs to the LAC Cyber Competence Centre. A full list needs to be established here from the analysis of the commitments deriving in a style of the current exemplary showcase above under section 5.1.

6. CONCLUSION

For this interim version, an initial set of dialogues has been identified and also resulting commitments such as action plans, roadmaps, joint declarations, statements etc. The interim version lays out the different steps and sources that consortium partners used and are undergoing in order to compile the most important and relevant information for identifying the main actors in digital dialogues on an EU-LAC level, but also multilateral level or bi-national level such as between the EU and individual LAC countries. Besides the main themes of the project SPIDER from the beginning to be focused upon, other themes are mentioned in the commitments also including ethical or linguistical aspects of AI, just to mention a specific example here.

For a more comprehensive mapping for the final deliverable the initial list of dialogues identified so far will be screened and showcased like the exemplary commitments in this interim review in order to identify the main actors and bring them together e.g. for the Dialogues Implementation Forum under SPIDER, the Twinning Programme or the Focus Groups.